

Performing Arts as a Limit to the Digital: Theatrical Space, Embodied Co-Presence, and the Politics of Ephemeral Action

The following text is an expanded version of my presentation at the workshop "AI and the Performing Arts," organized by the Department of Theater at the School of Fine Arts of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki on January 15, 2026.

Introduction: The Performing Arts as a Limit to the Digital

The global expansion of digital communication has intensified the algorithmic structuring of social life. However, the expansion of AI applications comes with a veil of obscurantist propaganda. We don't consider, for example, that a large part of annotation, that is, labeling data so that it can be used in data centers for AI training, is done by low-paid workers in sweatshops of the global South. In other words, there is no technology floating in the air. Behind it all are human suffering, cost, and powerful political entities that support AI investments, with no definite results so far. So we have to be very clear that there is a propaganda of instituted technophilia behind the use of digital machines, and especially AI. As Kate Crawford noted, even before the recent AI boom:

"Artificial intelligence, then, is an idea, an infrastructure, an industry, a form of exercising power, and a way of seeing; it's also a manifestation of highly organized capital backed by vast systems of extraction and logistics, with supply chains that wrap around the entire planet." [Crawford 2019]

Yet not all human activities are equally susceptible to digitization. This article advances the hypothesis that the performing arts—especially theater—constitute a structural limit to the digital. Their defining condition is the live gathering of embodied, vulnerable, "suffering" individuals, whose co-presence generates a unique field of meaning that cannot be reproduced by computational systems (Phelan 1993; Fischer-Lichte 2008; Auslander 1999).

In ontological terms, digital mechanisms and performing arts are social-historical creations and realizations of social imaginary significations.

Cornelius Castoriadis points out the distinctiveness of the social-historical mode of being.

"In being, in having-to-be, the social-historical element emerges, itself a rupture of being and an 'instance' of the appearance of otherness. The social-historical is radical imaginary, namely the incessant originating of otherness that figures, and figures itself, is in figuring and in figuring itself, giving itself as a figure and figuring itself to the second degree ('reflexively')." (Castoriadis 1987: 204)

Each society creates its proper historical time leaning on the inescapable flow of natural time, and both temporal strata participate in the creation of social reality. As such, society creates its own basic institutions of expression, communication, and identification, *"by the institution of legein, the ineffaceable component of language and of social representation, and the institution of teukhein, the ineffaceable component of social doing."* (Castoriadis 1987: 175)

We should note that, in general, both technology and art rely on both language and doing, but in different degrees, with different priorities, that institute different modes of association with reality. Technology uses the knowledge provided by language to transform reality practically. Art uses the means provided by technology to interpret reality imaginatively. However, the first, natural stratum of temporality does not exhaust all there is.

"The social-historical institution of temporality is not, and cannot be, a repetition or an extension of natural temporality - any more than the social-historical institution of identity, for example, can be the repetition or the extension of a natural identity." (Castoriadis, 1987: 202)

Every social institution and artifact is an actualization of imaginary temporality within natural temporality, imposing regularities and patterns of social being on the magmatic flow of becoming. Thus, social time includes imaginary and natural temporal strata as the nexus of the subjective and collective time, but not every social creation participates in all.

Technology is determined by the principle of utility, producing useful artifacts, whereas art is defined by the principle of imaginary interpretation and is self-contained in significance. Technology relies on the natural attributes of temporal repetition and entropic irreversibility, whereas art creates arbitrary narrative temporalities of imaginary potentialities.

Digital technology is, by definition, an intentional modification of natural temporality that relies on the quantifiable, digitizable, and measurable parameters of information. Digital cyberspace is characterized by algorithmic predetermination that produces an oscillatory, repetitive temporality (Stiegler 1998; Chun 2016). Digital environments create a pseudo-public projection of private communication, undermining the conditions of genuine public space (Crary 2013).

The temporal field of telecommunication is, by definition, private and solitary, based on the absence of physical co-existence.

The digital temporality of AI is the artificial, computational time-structure through which AI systems process data, make decisions, and generate meaning—one that collapses past, present, and future into a manipulable, non-human temporal field (Hansen 2004; Hayles 1999).

During digital computation, the appearance of an error means the failure of the mechanism, a breakdown of the algorithmic execution. Digital functions operate on an externally adjusted temporality.

As such, the internal digital temporality of AI differs fundamentally from human, biological, and historical temporality. The temporal regime produced by computational processes is characterized by non-linearity, since AI can access past data instantly and operate outside chronological sequence, asynchronicity, since AI processes occur in micro-temporal scales—nanoseconds, cycles, parallel threads—alien to human perception, predictivity, since AI models generate anticipatory outputs, and archival flattening, since AI treats the past as a manipulable dataset rather than lived history (Stiegler 1998; Chun 2016).

Meaning enters the digital mechanism exogenously as a command, a set of rules, and a specific data input to be analysed and restructured as an output, whose significance is defined in relation to the user. Nevertheless, exploring a place on Google Maps is not like actually going there.

All the visual arts, music, and literature are within the realm of digitization. LLMs are excellent machines of image and language manipulation, analysis, and reassembly in the form of patterns. But AI can generate without understanding (Dreyfus 1992; Cantwell Smith 2019).

LLMs are built on deep learning using neural network architectures known as Transformers with "self-attention" mechanisms that weigh the significance of specific data parts in order to analyze context and relationships between words. AI can generate, but cannot understand poetry. For AI, it's the same thing: whatever you give it, a catalog, an image, or Beethoven's Fifth Symphony, or T.S. Eliot's *The Waste Lands*, all are rendered into data patterns.

However, LLMs can reproduce such patterns, so the user, as a subject, is emotionally moved. Why? Because AI is a machine of statistical analysis and data folding, to emotionally move the user. It produces a subjective emotional response within the subject, rather than in the system.

Today, the most advanced agentic AI operates within the cyberspace of telecommunication as an agent without subjectivity, a sophisticated tool of data and user manipulation. Rather than being ethereal, AI is a techno-industrial system, *"both embodied and material, made from natural resources, fuel, human labor, infrastructures, logistics, histories, and classifications."* (Crawford 2019)

The colonization of all social domains by AI technology is driven by powerful political and financial interests that circumvent copyright legislation in a way that renders all visual arts as raw data for AI training. In 2025, the government of Japan sold the rights of Ghibli Studios animations to OpenAI, which led to a flood of Miyazaki-style AI-generated content across the Internet. This appropriation of art is a sign of digital barbarism. (Schismenos 2025)

Why can the performing arts resist this? In my opinion, because they presuppose, by definition, the live gathering of suffering bodies and constitute, by definition, a fleeting and temporal intersubjective field of coexistence between the artist and the audience, which is defined par excellence by physical communication.

Zhu-Nowell, the Assistant Curator at the Guggenheim Museum in New York, clarified this distinction as follows:

"So performance is a form of art that happens at a particular time in a particular place, where the artist engages in some sort of activity, usually before an audience. The main difference between performance art and other modes of visual art practices, such as painting, photography, and sculpture, is that it is a temporal event or action."

<https://www.guggenheim.org/audio/track/performance-art-versus-performing-arts>

Performing arts (dance, theater, performance) are temporary, live, and embodied, requiring a specific time, place, and interaction with an audience. Unlike static visual arts (painting, sculpture), which produce lasting, tangible objects, performative arts are dynamic, process-driven events that exist only in

the moment of creation, often using the performer's body as the primary medium. These create their own mode of common time that cannot be contained in digital temporality.

In early 2026, research conducted by Peiyang Song, Pengrui Han, and Noah Goodman concluded that Large Language Models fundamentally fail to reproduce human reasoning. The researchers found that *"even advanced LLMs struggle with abstract reasoning tasks, such as inferring underlying rules from limited examples, understanding implicit conceptual relationships, and reliably handling symbolic or temporal abstractions."* (Song et al. 2026)

Performing arts are a different and distinctly human mode of "reliable handling symbolic or temporal abstractions", characterized by the symbolic, elliptic representation of imaginary time and space, as represented and enacted on stage.

Theatrical Space and Time: Embodied Co-Presence

Performative and theatrical space and time are defined by actual presence, as opposed to telepresence, and the physical parameters of personal orientation (front/back, up/down). This is not a predetermined mathematical space, but the open space of experience (Merleau-Ponty 1945; Casey 1997). They are structured by the rhythm of collective interaction, transforming private experience into public time.

An artistic performance creates a multilayered imaginary space, the narrative/dramatic space of the text, and the performative space of the stage, that inhabits real physical space. This is what Fischer-Lichte (2008) calls the autopoietic feedback loop between actors and spectators.

An artistic performance creates a multilayered imaginary space, the narrative/dramatic space of the text and the performative space of the stage, that inhabits real physical space, the architectural theater, with set design functioning as a bridge between reality and imaginary representation. Accordingly, it creates an Imaginary time, the temporal structure of the narrative and performance, within the flow of historical time, the social situation anchoring the performance in the present. The boundaries of stage space are fluid, and dramatic time is always open to the network of social time. Meaning emerges interpersonally through experiential discourse, integrating intellectual, emotional, and aesthetic dimensions.

Physical presence is a fundamental element of theatrical space-time, which is thus defined by the parameters of the physical body. That is, front-back, up-down. For every actor or spectator, the performance takes place within the dimensions of front and back, up and down, close and far in relation to their bodily presence in the here-and-now of the performance.

These define the rhythm of collective interaction, and this also has to do with the free emergence of otherness, that is, the beneficial presence of error. In other words, error can help imagination break loose.

Error, contingency, and improvisation are not failures but generative forces (Schechner 1985; Turner 1969). Error can become an invention, or it can open up a new space of performative affordances on

the common field of intersubjective phenomenological participation, that is, the intertwining of minds, souls, and bodies. So performing arts interact on all three levels of experience, that is, on the intellectual level through language and gesture, on the emotional level through expression and passion, and on the sensorial level through scent, spectacle, physical immersion, and touch. Performing arts project meaning on intellectual, emotional, and sensorial levels simultaneously.

The temporal field of performing acts is by definition the intersubjective present, immersing the distinct subjective temporalities of the spectators and actors within a meaningful, self-contained narrative whole.

Whereas performing arts embrace contingency, digital systems suppress it. Whereas performing arts generate meaning through embodied co-presence, digital systems generate responses through computation.

The temporality inherent in performing arts means that dramatic performance is not simply an artistic medium; it is a mode of social existence. Its temporality is ephemeral, its space relational, and its meaning emerges through embodied interaction. These characteristics position theatrical performance as a counter-form to the digital: where digital systems rely on repetition, classification, and algorithmic predictability, theater thrives on contingency, error, and the unpredictable emergence of otherness.

The importance of the performing arts is becoming political again in terms of public coexistence. There is a demand for the intensity of in-person presence, in terms of what theatrical action is, which we suddenly discover is created on the imaginary field of emotive significations between the audience and the artists.

It lies in the discomfort that a theatrical or dance performance can cause to the audience and in the protest that can occur within this living interaction, which is both interpersonal and public.

That is why theater, dance, and performance differ from cinema in terms of temporality, the former being enacted at present, the latter being a re-projection of the past. As Peter Brook noticed in *The Empty Space*:

"There is only one interesting difference between the cinema and the theatre. The cinema flashes onto a screen images from the past. As this is what the mind does to itself all through life, the cinema seems intimately real. Of course, it is nothing of the sort—it is a satisfying and enjoyable extension of the unreality of everyday perception. The theatre, on the other hand, always asserts itself in the present. This is what can make it more real than the normal stream of consciousness. This also is what can make it so disturbing." (Brook 1968)

Cinema belongs to a type of sequential narrative by visual imagery, which is closer to comics and photography, and, in extension, to the digitalization of the recorded past. Cinema re-projects the past; theatre enacts the present (Brook 1968). This distinction is central to performance theory (Auslander 1999; Phelan 1993; Schneider 2011). Performing arts involve embodied co-presence, whereas cinema and digital media rely on mechanical repetition. Performing arts involve three dimensions of intersubjective association in the present, as exemplified by theatre.

The Three Dimensions of Theatrical Action

Theatrical action can be analytically understood through three interrelated dimensions—religious, political, and existential—each of which reveals a different aspect of its resistance to digital rendering.

The religious origins of theater emphasize communal belonging, ritual imitation, and ecstatic separation from ordinary life (Burkert 1985; Schechner 1985; Turner 1969). This dimension foregrounds theater's capacity to generate collective presence, a phenomenon irreducible to digital mediation, which lacks the physical and affective density of ritual co-presence.

We are dealing with the religious dimension, which is original, expressed through ritual, imitation, and common immersion within the theatrical representation. It is a pre-theatrical, but originally performative dimension and a necessary, but not sufficient, condition for dramatic art. As such, it is a manifestation of the social imaginary and an expression of humanity's quest for meaning beyond the world of appearances, by transforming the appearance of the world.

Then there is the political dimension, which marks a break with tradition, when the rigidity of religious rituals is abandoned in favour of the free imaginative play of the theatrical act. On the Parian Chronicle, a Hellenistic chronology, covering the years from 1582 BC to 299 BC, inscribed on a stele we find that on year 534 BCE Thespis, an Athenian poet transformed the choral performances of dithyrambs by introducing a character who could engage in dialogue with the chorus, thus creating the theatrical space and time, the public space and time of performative dialogue.

Classical Athenian theater was embedded in the democratic polis (Goldhill 1999; Ober 2008). Plato's "theatrocracy" captures this intertwining of performance and politics. Arendt argues that drama uniquely preserves the revelatory quality of action. (Arendt 1958)

The political dimension of theater lies in its capacity to stage subjectivity, judgment, and responsibility within a shared public space. Theater is the political art par excellence because it transfers the political sphere of human life into artistic form. As Arendt notes, only drama can "reframe" action through imitation while preserving its revelatory quality, since *"the drama comes fully to life only when it is enacted in the theater. Only the actors and speakers who re-enact the story's plot can convey the full meaning..."* (Arendt 1958: 187)

Aristotle gave us the first definition of tragedy in his *Poetics*:

"Tragedy, then, is an imitation of an action that is serious, complete, and of a certain magnitude; in language embellished with each kind of artistic ornament, the several kinds being found in separate parts of the play; in the form of action, not of narrative; through pity and fear affecting the proper purgation of these emotions."

He goes on to point out that *"Tragedy is the imitation of an action; and an action implies personal agents,"* and as such, it can be distinguished by epic poetry in terms of narrative method. Being the actualization of a plot through live imitation, tragedy, and theatre in general, is defined by action rather than mere representation, meaning that it consists of a living activity and produces an active effect.

"Tragedy is an imitation, not of men, but of an action and of life, and life consists in action, and its end is a mode of action, not a quality."

This is an Attic tragedy, of course, where ritual is transformed into dramatic interpretation. Where? In the public space of the open theatre. In what context? As a form of artistic competition. Who judges the contestants? The audience. Theater is performed by the artists for the audience. By a collective for society, because drama must be performed publicly before an audience. Why must it be performed before an audience? Because there, in the space and time between the artists and the audience, is where passion lies, and that is where pity and fear lie. The theater is the political dimension of the apparent reflection of society presented in front of itself.

Arendt argued that the specific living quality of action and speech is so inextricably linked to the living flow of speech that it can only be represented through a kind of repetition of action in the public sphere. A painter or a composer may address the world, God, the universe, the abyss, or nothingness. A performative artist always addresses the living public audience.

"This is also why the theater is the political art par excellence; only there is the political sphere of human life transposed into art. By the same token, it is the only art whose sole subject is man in his relationship to others." (Arendt 1958: 188).

The political dimension offers sufficient and necessary conditions for theatre.

The third dimension, maintained before and beyond the imitation of politics, is the existential. The existential dimension of theater confronts the abyss between internal and external, past and future. This existential openness resists algorithmic closure (Lehmann 2006; Phelan 1993).

A striking contemporary example of the political force of live performance is the work of Belarus Free Theatre during the 2020–2021 protests against the Lukashenko regime. When mass demonstrations erupted after the contested presidential election, the company—already banned in Belarus—continued to stage clandestine performances in apartments, warehouses, and forests. These events required the physical gathering of bodies under conditions of surveillance, repression, and personal risk. Their performances, such as *Dogs of Europe* (2020), became acts of civil disobedience: the audience's mere presence constituted a political gesture.

Theatre there functioned not as representation but as embodied dissent, creating a temporary public sphere that could not be digitized or mediated without losing its force. The political significance of these performances lay precisely in their ephemerality, co-presence, and shared vulnerability—qualities that no algorithmic or telematic environment can reproduce. Theatrical action became a form of lived resistance, a reclaiming of public time against the state's apparatus of surveillance and digital control.

A second, equally compelling example of politically charged theatrical action is the wave of embodied protest-performances by Iranian women in 2023, following the death of Mahsa (Jina) Amini in police custody. Although the initial uprising began in late 2022, the performative dimension of the movement intensified throughout 2023, taking the form of public, embodied, and ephemeral acts of defiance that functioned as political theatre in the most literal sense.

One of the most iconic gestures was the public removal and burning of the hijab, performed in streets, squares, university courtyards, and even inside metro stations. These acts were not symbolic in the abstract; they were live, embodied performances enacted under conditions of immediate danger. Women stood on utility boxes, benches, or car roofs, cutting their hair in front of crowds who

responded with chants, rhythmic clapping, and protective circles of bodies. The audience was not passive: their presence transformed the act into a collective performance of civil courage.

The political significance of these performances lay precisely in their embodied vulnerability. A woman standing unveiled in a Tehran street, surrounded by others who risk arrest simply by witnessing her, enacts a form of political theatre that no digital medium can replicate. The act is meaningful because it is live, dangerous, and unpredictable—qualities that algorithmic systems are designed to eliminate.

In this context, the Iranian women's movement demonstrates how theatre emerges spontaneously wherever bodies gather to reclaim public time. These performances were not staged art events, yet they possessed all the structural features of theatrical action: a performer, an audience, a shared space, a charged temporality, and a political horizon. Their power derived from the irreducibility of embodied presence, confirming that certain forms of human action remain fundamentally beyond the reach of digital mediation.

Theatrical action oscillates between heteronomy, the reinforcement of tradition, and autonomy, the challenge to tradition. This existential openness resists the closure characteristic of algorithmic systems, since the existential human condition is the basis of both tragedy and comedy. Comedy is any tragedy viewed from an ironic distance, and tragedy is any comedy that we suffer by identification with the characters. This reminds us of what is human and is not, like Terence said:

Homo sum, humani nihil a me alienum puto: "I am human, nothing that is human is alien to me."

Only the theater can do that, make us feel that we live. We see people in front of us, not any screen we can turn off. The other day, I found myself in a performance that made me feel very uncomfortable. I strongly disagreed with the interpretation of the play, but I accepted it. I couldn't leave, both out of politeness and because you don't leave the theater, because if you do, something happens. So this has to do with the relationship between the individual and the community, whether that community is what we call the audience or the acting community that performs.

Conclusion: Performing arts as a Form of Free Public Time

Theater has historically served as a privileged site for exploring fundamental philosophical distinctions between Being, as represented by the actors, and Appearing, as represented by the costumes, and also between Being, as presented by the characters, and Becoming, as presented by the plot, within the interplay of private and public space.

These dualities reveal theater as a medium where appearance becomes a mode of truth-seeking, and where the individual negotiates their position within the collective. The social-historical dimension of theater is thus co-substantive with the democratic revolution: it stages the tension between the personal and the communal, the contingent and the meaningful.

Theater occupies the intersection of event, narrative, and signification. An event is a meaningful sequence of circumstances; a narrative is the presentation of such sequences. Historical narrative remains open and revisable, whereas poetic narrative forms a closed whole of exemplary events.

Historical time is intertwined with social action, generating past fields of experience and future horizons of expectation. Historical narratives, by contrast, selectively organize events toward a specific end. Theater, situated between these two forms, produces a unique mode of truth: the truth of embodied witnessing. Aeschylus, both a warrior in the Persian Wars and dramatist of the *Persians* tragedy, exemplifies this fusion of lived experience and poetic representation.

In the field of art and in the field of meanings, and especially in the political field, the theatrical Act can bring back that sense of community, reminding us that the digital representation has its limits, and those are the limits of digitization. This means that digital technology cannot use theater, but theater can use digital technology. When a director decides to project videos on stage, these become part of the live theatrical performance. A theatrical performance cannot be absorbed by the screen. The experience is different. Every video is a mechanical repetition. Every play itself, but also every performance of it, is a distinct theatrical event. There, amidst living roles, is the ephemeral art of living bodies.

If the hypothesis advanced here is correct, performing arts represent a crucial limit to digitalization. Their insistence on embodied co-presence, ephemeral temporality, and intersubjective meaning-making positions them as limits to the algorithmic normalization of social life. In an era of digital surveillance and mediated communication, performing arts like theatre reactivate the possibility of free public time, where individuals encounter one another not as data points but as vulnerable, acting beings. As Castoriadis noted:

"It is precisely because the modern social imaginary has no flesh of its own, it is because it borrows its substance from the rational, from one moment of the rational which it thus transforms into a pseudorational, that it is doomed to crisis and to erosion and that modern society contains within it the 'objective' possibility of a transformation of what up to now has been the role of the imaginary in history." (Castoriadis 1987: 160)

The performing arts ensure that human action continues to pass through the embodied, communal language of lived experience.

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